

Asian Open Access: Regional Survey

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Introduction

This report presents the results of a survey of open access activities in Asia undertaken in early 2017. The survey was carried out by [Asia OA](#), a special forum hosted by COAR (Confederation of Open Access Repositories) supporting members of the Asian open access community to share information, meet each other and foster relationships.

The continent of Asia is rapidly increasing in prominence on the world stage, both in terms of R&D as well as scientific production. According to the UNESCO World Science Report (2015), the region encompasses “close to half of global economic output (45%) and expenditure on research and development (R&D, 42%) and is home to both some of the world’s most dynamic technological powerhouses”¹. In terms of research outputs, the Asian continent is already prolific and is growing quickly, with China poised to become the world’s leading country in terms of number of published research articles.²

As with other continents, open access policies and practices are being adopted in Asia, although progress varies greatly across the different jurisdictions and locations. This report provides an account of the current state of open access in 16 regions of Asia. It is expected that the survey results will contribute to the adoption of open access and help various regions make the case for greater investment in open access, both in terms of policies, as well as national and local infrastructure.

¹ UNESCO Science Report: Towards 2030. Available at https://en.unesco.org/unesco_science_report/asia

² UNESCO Science Report: Towards 2030. Available at https://en.unesco.org/unesco_science_report/asia

Some general observations from the survey are as follows:

- All regions that responded to the survey are active in terms of open access, but many do not yet have a cohesive strategy. Many regions also lack funding to develop the infrastructure needed to support open access. As a result, OA activities are often very distributed and uncoordinated, which ultimately reduces their impact.
- There is often a mismatch in terms of policy, funding and practices. While some governments approve of open access, there are gaps in both policy adoption and funding to build and maintain the local infrastructure that supports open access.
- Engagement at the continental level through Asia OA can help countries make progress in their local environments. It offers a forum whereby participants can share experiences and examples that demonstrate that OA is an international trend, and provide a variety of models that are working successfully in Asia.

Survey Results

Responding Regions	
1. Bangladesh	9. Myanmar
2. China	10. Nepal
3. Hong Kong	11. Pakistan
4. India	12. Philippines
5. Indonesia	13. Singapore
6. Japan	14. South Korea
7. Malaysia	15. Taiwan
8. Mongolia	16. Thailand

I. Open access policies

Links to regional policies

China <http://or.nsfc.gov.cn/policies?locale=en>

Hong Kong Hidden at the back of UGC guidelines are policies stating (subject to the publisher's agreement) researchers should deposit a copy of their publication in his/her institutional repository no later than six months after publication or the embargo period. This is not enforced in any way and nobody knows about it though, so probably can't be called a policy
http://www.ugc.edu.hk/doc/eng/rgc/form/srfdp_sr2.pdf

India The Departments of Biotechnology and Science & Technology had jointly adopted Open Access policy for its funded research
<http://www.dbtindia.nic.in/wp-content/uploads/APPROVED-OPEN-ACCESS-POLICY-DBTDST12.12.2014.pdf>. The Wellcome Trust/DBT India Alliance (the 'India Alliance') supports "unrestricted access to the published output of research" <http://www.wellcomedbt.org/award-policies>

Japan Doctoral dissertation shall be made public through the Internet according to the Degree Regulations http://www.mext.go.jp/a_menu/koutou/daigakuin/detail/1331796.htm
<http://law.e-gov.go.jp/htmldata/S28/S28F03501000009.html>

Myanmar EIFL funded Open Access policies and assisted Repository setup. Find out more: About EIFL in Myanmar <http://www.eifl.net/country/myanmar> "AN AMAZING YEAR FOR OPEN ACCESS IN MYANMAR" <http://www.eifl.net/blogs/amazing-year-open-access-myanmar>

Nepal International Centre for Integrated Mountain Development (ICIMOD) has Open Access Policy. According to this the research fellows and research grant recipients must publish their research reports in an Open Access medium.

Philippines The IRRI policies on open access and open data comes from the CGIAR policies: <http://www.cgiar.org/resources/open-access/> CGIAR has made a strong commitment to Open

Access and Open Data (OA-OD), hence all research institutions within CGIAR (including IRRI) adhere to this policy (<http://www.cgiar.org/resources/open-access/>). Donor entities also require OA-OD, such as Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation Open Access Policy (<http://www.gatesfoundation.org/how-we-work/general-information/open-access-policy>), USAID Open Data Policy (<http://www.usaid.gov/ads/policy/500/579>).

Singapore A*STAR OA policy (self-archiving, no later than 12 months after publication, grant money can be used to cover APC) <http://roarmap.eprints.org/44/>
 National Medical Research Council (NMRC) OA policy (self-archiving, no later than 12 months after publication, grant money can be used to cover APC)
http://www.nmrc.gov.sg/content/nmrc_internet/home/top_nav/download.html
 National Research Foundation (NRF) requests grant receiving organisations to have OA policies in place (no link available). Nanyang Technological University (NTU) OA policy requires all NTU staff to deposit their final peer-reviewed manuscript of journal articles and conference papers electronically to the Digital Repository (DR-NTU) maintained by the Library upon acceptance of their publications and all non-confidential PhD & research theses to be made open access
<http://www.ntu.edu.sg/Library/Pages/open-access.aspx>
 Singapore Management University (SMU) OA policy
https://library.smu.edu.sg/sites/default/files/library/pdf/smuopenaccesspolicy_24102013.pdf

Taiwan The major funding agency (Ministry of Science and Technology) does not specify any open access requirement in the policy
<https://www.most.gov.tw/most/attachments/4072d706-f235-4cce-9607-517d05aaob35>

II. Open access repositories

Regional coverage of open access repositories

Bangladesh In Bangladesh, Institutional repositories have been seen as an unprecedented opportunity to provide equality of access to essential research information and to raising awareness of national research. Along with a number of institutional repositories (Dhaka University Institutional Repository), about 10 agricultural research repositories have been established in Bangladesh, as well as other domain repositories like the Digital Repository of the International Center for Diarrhoeal Disease Research.

China Many universities in China have a repository. It mainly depends on their open access policies or institutional repository policy or some university librarians' motivation.

Hong Kong [All 8 universities](#) in Hong Kong have institutional repositories. The HKU one has just been upgraded to become a CRIS.

India Out of 677 universities in India, 315 Universities had signed MoUs with UGC/Inflibnet, and 287 universities are contributing to the Shodhganga amounting to 143800 thesis in the repository. (<http://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/>). In addition, 36 state/deemed agricultural universities are contributing to the Krishi Prabha (<http://krishikosh.egranth.ac.in/handle/1/466>). Open Access archive harvester for DBT/DST repositories <http://sciencecentral.in/>

Indonesia In general, all institution with libraries have their own repositories, including universities.

Japan 56.5% of the universities in Japan have a repository.

Malaysia All public universities in Malaysia have their own IR.

Mongolia One of our partners created own IR. <http://repository.ufe.edu.mn/> but they do not have an institutional policy.

Myanmar Two universities in Myanmar (University of Yangon and Mandalay) have repositories right now. University of Yangon Repository can be accessed at <http://uyr.uy.edu.mm> and University of Mandalay Open Access Repository at <http://umoar.mu.edu.mm/>

Nepal Some institutions have their own institutional repositories but those are in grass-roots level. Nepal Library and Information Consortium (NeLIC) has established a Central Open Access

Repository in Nepal welcoming all institutions to join and provide their publication for open access. Similarly ICIMOD has run HimalDoc and Open Access digital repository.

Pakistan 20% of the universities in Pakistan have a repository.

Philippines For DOST, they have an [IRODs repository](#) for collaboration data that are declared open, and various projects deposit data here.

Singapore Most universities in Singapore have repositories, but some are only accessible to staff/students.

South Korea There are 30 IRs in South Korea: 14 universities, 10 research institutes, and 6 public organizations.

Taiwan 127 out of 159 universities (including public and private) have an institutional repository, in addition to the Taiwan Academic Institutional Repository. <http://tair.org.tw/>

Thailand about 20% coverage

-There are currently 11 OA repositories listed in OpenDOAR.

-University libraries implement IRs to publish intellectual outputs such as CUIR- Chulalongkorn University Intellectual Repository.

-Research Library of the National Research Council of Thailand (NRCT) is a national depository of research reports and theses which are collected from local universities and research organizations. Under the Science and Technology Knowledge Services project, initiatives like Thai Thesis Database, Online Resources, Thailibrary.org, eBooks, and eLearning were taken up, giving a major fillip to the Thai content.

-Thai LIS Consortium is working to promote and advocate Open Access concept by developing OA resources using in-house application, such as Thai Academic Reference Database.

-The national repository, Thai National Research Repository (TNRR) houses and publishes research reports funded by four national institutions: National Science and Technology Agency (NSTDA), National Research Council of Thailand, Thailand Research Fund, and Health System Research Institute.

<http://www.unesco.org/new/en/communication-and-information/portals-and-platforms/goap/access-by-region/asia-and-the-pacific/thailand/> <http://www.opendoar.org/find.php> (search Thailand)

III. Open access journals

Local open access journals

Bangladesh Most of the 85 universities in Bangladesh publish some journals in their respective disciplines. The majority of these journals are in printed form only and very few of them are accessible via the internet. Since only four journals are cited by the WoS JCR, it is not difficult to guess at the low standing of the other journals.

BanglaJOL is a database of 140 journals published in Bangladesh, covering the full range of academic disciplines. Bangladesh Journals OnLine (BanglaJOL) was initiated in June 2007 and officially launched in September 2007. BanglaJOL is now hosted by Ubiquity Press. The objective of BanglaJOL is to give greater visibility to the participating journals, and to the research they convey.

China In terms of natural science, China has almost 400 OA journals and in the social science, there are over 600 journals. See <http://www.oaj.cas.cn/> and <http://www.nssd.org/about.aspx?id=7>

Hong Kong Some medical journals registered in Hong Kong (although actually based in mainland China) calling themselves open access, but don't have any information on licensing. Elsevier has a few subsidised society journals in HK (e.g. Hong Kong Journal of Nephrology and Hong Kong Physiotherapy Journal) that say they are open access, but are under CC-BY NC ND licenses. Then there is GigaScience ([COI statement: my journal] that is true CC-BY OA.

India There are a number of open access journals published in India, including all 18 journals published by the CSIR (Council of Scientific and Industrial Research) are Open Access

(<http://www.niscair.res.in/ScienceCommunication/ResearchJournals/rejour/rejouri.htm>) and ICAR (Indian Council of Agricultural Research), which is hosting about 30 journals online, most of which are Open Access (<http://epubs.icar.org.in/ejournal/index.php/index>). ROAD (<http://road.issn.org>) lists 1855 journals/resources DOAJ (<https://doaj.org>) lists 244 journals.

Indonesia Indonesia has a platform called One Search Indonesia, managed by the National Library. The platform allows public to search for content from repositories all over Indonesia adopting Open Journal System.

Japan J-STAGE (Japan Science and Technology Information Aggregator, Electronic) by JST (Japan Science and Technology Agency) provides 1,891 e-journal. Almost all of them are open access journals. The department bulletin has been circulated natively as free exchange, and now repository became their institutional platform of distribution. In DOAJ 9,517 journals, 25 journals are counted as their "country of publisher" is Japan.

Malaysia Less than 5% of the journals in Malaysia are open access.

Mongolia We are supporting open access journals platform which is www.mongoliajol.info since 2010.

Myanmar Journals in Myanmar are not digitally available yet.

Nepal Nepal has several open access journals, some of which are listed in Nepal journals Online (NepJol) <http://nepjol.info/>

Pakistan Several resources can be noted:

- PakMediNet is a comprehensive website aims to promote Pakistani Based Medical Research and Pakistani Medical Journals on the Internet

- Pakistan Research Repository The Higher Education Commission (HEC) was set up by the Government of Pakistan to facilitate the development of indigenous universities to be world-class centers of education, research and development

- Iqbal Cyber Library is most remarkable Urdu website providing Open Access. Iqbal Cyber Library inaugurated by the President of Pakistan on 21st April 2003 is the first digital library of Urdu also known as virtual library of Urdu language

- Imas, Turjman-a-Quran, Tazkeer, Ishraq, Suayharam, Nida-e-Khilafat, Meesaq, Hikmat-e-Quran, Al-Sharia, Toluislam, Minhaj-ul-Quran, Dukhtran-e-Islam, Al-Ulama, Eeqaz and Jadeed Adab, are prominent Open Access Urdu journals. All these journals are on different aspects of Islam except Almas that is on Urdu Literature.

- A number, of journals of different universities (public and private) are available. University of the Punjab, Government College University Lahore, Bahauddin Zakariya University Multan, University of Karachi, and Lahore School of Economics are some of prominent universities providing open access to their journals.

-And others: Pakistan Journal of Information Management & Libraries (PJIM&L) 6. Pakistan Journal of Biotechnology 7. International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research 8. Pakistanaat: A Journal of Pakistan Studies 9. JPMS, the Journal of Pioneering Medical Sciences 10 Pakistan Journal of Nuclear Medicine 11 Pakistan Journal of Ophthalmology 12 Asian Journal of Agriculture and Biology 13 PAKISTAN VETERINARY JOURNAL 14 Pakistan Journal of Ophthalmology 15 Pakistan Journal of Physiology - Pakistan Physiological Society and many others

Philippines In the science field, an online journal /repository publishes with open access (Philippine Science and Technology Journal Online - <http://philscitech.org/>), so this is an example of repository of publications of research made by local scientists but published internationally (through this journal).

Singapore Open access journals in Singapore:

- The Raffles Bulletin of Zoology (by NUS/the Lee Kong Chian Natural History Museum) <http://lkcnhm.nus.edu.sg/nus/index.php/nhmpublications/rbz>
- Singapore Medical Journal (by the Singapore Medical Association) <http://www.smj.org.sg/>
- Singapore Journal of Library and Information Management (by the Library Association of Singapore) <http://www.las.org.sg/wp/sjlim/>
- International Journal of Nursing Sciences <http://www.journals.elsevier.com/international-journal-of-nursing-sciences/>
- Electronic Journal of Foreign Language Teaching (e-FLT) <http://e-flt.nus.edu.sg/>
- Research and Practice in Technology Enhanced Learning <http://www.telrp.com/>

South Korea Korea has about 70 open access science and technology journals, that apply CC licences.

Taiwan According to DOAJ, there are 31 open access journals in Taiwan. Most of these open access journals adopt CC BY-NC-ND licenses, with few exceptions for CC BY. However, no central support or policy is available for those journals. It largely depends on the institutional supports. For example, Zoological Studies published by Biodiversity Research Center, Academia Sinica is OA and free of page charge. But Statistica Sinica (published by Institute of Statistical Science, Academia Sinica) maintains a policy that full-text articles published a year ago are free to access.

Thailand According to DOAJ, there are 20 open access journals being published in Thailand. Thai Digital Collection project is a cooperative open access initiative aiming to collect theses, eBooks, and ejournal collections of research output from different universities in Thailand coordinated by Office of Information Technology for Development Studies, which has also taken up a Thai Union Catalogue project.

IV. Centralized support and funding

Other local information

Bangladesh Through “Digital Bangladesh Vision 2021” the government is trying to popularize and establish the open access concept among the students, researchers, academics and policy makers.

Hong Kong More information can be found at: <https://osf.io/3egzh/>
<http://www.slideshare.net/GigaScience/scott-edmunds-hong-kong-open-access-update>

India The [Open Access India](#), a community of practice had prepared and submitted a draft ‘National Open Access Policy’ which is available at: <https://goo.gl/KBRj49>

Nepal NeLIC, the only consortium in Nepal, has mentioned open access as one of their objectives. They are also working with the Nepal government to encourage the adoption of an open access policy.

Thailand Some are provided by A central library of NSTDA, known as Science and Technology Knowledge Services (STKS), has initiated several OA projects since 1990s. These include NSTDA Research, Thai Glossary, Thai S&T Encyclopedia, e-Learning, and Bibliography of ASEAN Studies. <http://www.nstda.or.th/thairesearch/>. Some are offered by EIFL Thailand

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